

Visiting Maurice Halbwachs in the Collective Memory

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Abstract

A toy, a medal, a pillow, a ring, a drawing ... We all have things that evoke positive memories. These “memory artifacts” incorporate experiences, which point to collective emotions and depict a successful relationship between people and the material world.

This paper emphasizes the importance of Memory Studies for the field of Design. Its main goal is to introduce some of Maurice Halbwachs’ pioneering ideas presented in his posthumous “La mémoire collective” and illustrate them with stories about things that bring back memories. These stories were taken from the research project entitled “Memory Artifacts of Everyday Life” conducted in the Social Sciences Graduate Program at the State University of Rio de Janeiro.

Keywords: affective memory; material memory; social memory; memory artifacts.

Introduction

This paper is part of the ongoing doctoral research project “Memory Artifacts of Everyday Life” about things that trigger “positive memories” and with which people establish ties of affection. Its purpose is to understand the essence and content that makes an artifact memorable.

This study was primarily based on anthropological field study methods, including participant observation and interviews with people from different backgrounds and experiences. It has been carried out in the light of authors who have brought important contributions to the field of Social Memory and by maintaining a constant exchange with designers.

The main purpose of this investigation is to provide guidelines so as to increase the participation of Design in the development of forms that will bring a deeper meaning to human existence and contribute to a more responsible and fraternal society.

On memory studies

Andreas Huyssen points out the emergence of memory as one of the most astonishing phenomenon in recent years. He observes that the modernist culture was energized by “present futures”, but since the 1980’s the focus has shifted to “present pasts” (Huyssen, 2000).

Memory studies have been growing within disciplines, which up to now were foreign to the subject and amassing varying and divergent conclusions among their veteran scholars.

Memory seems to be in every step, idea and action. It is present in everything and everyone (Santos, 2003). So, if we are to understand the essence and content, which makes an artifact memorable, we must visit the field of Social Memory.

On Maurice Halbwachs

Maurice Halbwachs was one of the most contributing authors towards the understanding of collective memory. He was a disciple of Emile Durkheim, and believed deeply in the inseparability of the individual and society at all levels of existence.

Halbwachs treated memory as a social fact in a time when memory was primarily understood as an individual or subjective phenomenon (Santos, 2003). His last works were gathered in the book “The Collective Memory”, published after his death in a Nazi concentration camp. So, if we are to visit the field of Social Memory we must be introduced to Maurice Halbwachs and to his book “The Collective Memory”.

The collective memory by Maurice Halbwachs

We are never alone

Maurice Halbwachs starts off his book with the following disconcerting statement:

Our memories remain collective and are recalled to us through others even though only we were participants in the events or saw the things concerned. In reality, we are never alone. Other men need not be physically present, since we always carry with us a number of distinct persons. (Halbwachs, 1990: 26).

But what is meant by: “we are never alone”? After all, we can all recall events that were experienced alone and far from any witness. We all believe we have individual memories and even secret ones...

The author goes on to describe his first arrival in London and his strolls through the city. While walking with an architect, his attention is drawn to architecture; beside a historian, he learns where and how important events took place; with the painter he notices its plastic aspects and so on.

Halbwachs then makes it look as if he was strolling alone, but soon after he clarifies that he could not be alone. Actually, he would find in his memory a comment made by a historian friend, the image of a painter's picture, the impressions Dickens' book left on him and so on. What Halbwachs points out is that he was not alone in his reflections, since his thoughts moved within the groups composed of the architect, the historian, the painter, the novelist, among others. Commenting his first impressions of London, the author explains that:

Other men have already shared these same memories. Furthermore, they help me remember them: to better recall, I turn to them, I temporarily adopt their points of view, I join their group (...) and I find within myself many ideas and ways of thinking that I would never have arrived to on my own (Halbwachs, 1950: 3).

Things we remember and things we forget

According to Halbwachs, to remember or confirm a memory we don't need the presence or the statements of witnesses, but rather the communion with their memories and the identification with their ideas and ways of thinking.

Memory is connected to the social groups we belong to and within which we move through our thoughts. It is our attachment and detachment towards them that determine what we remember and forget. The passage recounted by one of our interviewees illustrates this idea:

I keep a lot of things that remind me my school days, my childhood, my friends (...) But some things I throw away without regret. I was so disgusted with an ex-boyfriend that I threw away everything that reminded me of him! The other day my brother was amazed because I couldn't remember the town where we (my brother, my ex and I) had camped out together. The more my brother spoke of this trip, the less I remember it! Do you know why? Because I threw away every last memento of that wretched person and - PUF! – he disappeared along with everything we shared together!

Halbwachs recognizes that we keep memories of situations that only we know, but he does not consider this fact proof that our memory does not need to rely on the memory of others. To illustrate this passage, the author makes us imagine that we went on a trip with some friends, taking with us preoccupations ignored by the rest of the group. Throughout this trip, everything we see, hear and perceive feeds our secret preoccupations and, at the same time, bring us closer to the group these preoccupations are associated to. After some time, while thinking of the trip, we do not remember it in the same way as our friends who were there with us.

One of our interviewees experienced a similar situation to the one described above:

A group of friends and I went to a congress in Lisbon. At the airport my boyfriend put a metal ring on my finger that he snapped off the lid of a soda can. Then he asks me to marry him. I traveled with the “ring” on my finger and my boyfriend in my mind. I thought about him all the time! The other day my friends were talking about the congress, looking at photographs, exchanging stories. It was so weird... My memories of the trip were completely different.

Social frameworks

According to Halbwachs, the individual is characterized by his degree of interaction in the scheme of social relations, and his private memories are rooted within diverse social frameworks and impregnated by his social existence.

Halbwachs believes that we do not have memories of our early childhood: we can remember events that have been told to us, but we do not have direct memories of them, for we are not yet social beings. The author admits there are exceptions, such as the event remembered by Benevuto Cellini who, at the age of three, picks up a scorpion to play with

and is rescued by his father. Halbwachs recognizes that children can have memories, but emphasizes that this is possible because it takes place alongside his family. (Halbwachs, 1990: 39).

In another example, Halbwachs explains the childhood experience recounted by the psychologist Charles Blondel's that takes place in an abandoned house. Blondel finds himself in trouble and alone. He fell in a water hole, and risked drowning and considers this memory to be personal. In this case, the family could not intervene, for it was absent and did not have any knowledge of what happened. Still, the author argues that Blondel was not really alone since he thought he was with his family.

The experience lived by one of our interviewees can be evaluated in light of this thought:

I lived in Brasilia from 1960 to 1964 because my father was in the armed forces. It was such an inhospitable and futuristic place! I was four years old (...) I will tell you something I have never told anyone before: I would look at those gnarled trees and imagine an army of robots invading the school. (...) They approached blinking their lights and speaking in a metallic voice. It is a personal memory. Only I experienced it.

According to Halbwachs' theory, these childhood memories took place within the social frameworks of family, school, the construction of Brasilia, science fiction cartoons and the armed forces, the interviewee was part of.

The collective nature of personal memories

Halbwachs observes that there are memories that we are free to evoke whenever we want and others that do not respond to our call as easily. The author explains that in the first case, these memories are part of a public domain and are present and accessible both to us and to others. Those memories that are not so easily evoked, on the other hand, "belong only to us and constitute our most exclusive possession" (Halbwachs, 1990: 49).

Among the artifacts we have been studying, many seem to have the objective of "evoking memories" which we do not want to forget and which we have no one to share, as is shown in the passage below:

My story with Giulio had no witnesses and, sometimes, I find myself doubting if it actually happened. A bibelot he gave me is the only material sign I have of him. I keep the bibelot in a very noticeable place, as a reminder that Giulio really existed.

Halbwachs considers that an individual memory is made of interactions between the numerous collective memories of the groups which he or she belongs. He argues that the more a memory seems personal, the more it is collective. Some of these intersections can be extremely complex and do not depend on our will.

The episode recounted by Peter Stallybrass (2000) in his book “Marx’s Coat” might help us to understand the idea exposed above. It involves a jacket the author was wearing during a congress session and that belonged to a dear deceased friend.

I was presenting a paper on the concept of the individual when I was literally overwhelmed. I could not continue reading (...) I began to cry (...) I realized that, for the first time since his death, Allon White had come back to me (...) While I wore that jacket, Allon wore me.

In trying to explain what happened to him, Stallybrass tells us how he had been struggling to remember his friend since his death. The author goes on to describe the circumstances in which Allon’s wife had given him the jacket, his academic interests, the many moments lived with Allon throughout various periods of his life, among other situations that had to do with the diverse social milieus to which he belonged.

What occurred with Stallybrass can be understood as a consequence of the complex intersection of different collective memories in which, we conclude, Allon’s jacket played a crucial role.

Autobiographical and historical memory

Halbwachs draws a sharp distinction between what he calls “autobiographical” memory and “historical” memory. The historical memory is an exterior memory and does not belong to us. It gathers events that we did not live, that we know through written records. The autobiographical memory, on the other hand, is internal, personal and completely ours. It exists with the living support of a group. In fact, it is the members of the group who mould that particular image of the past, which is transmitted in the present.

The author illustrates that his parents, being French in the period following the 1870-1871 war, developed habits and adopted traits that became part of their personalities:

When I want to imagine how we lived, how we thought at that time, it is to them that I turn my thoughts. (...) Unlike other times, this one lives in my memory (Halbwachs, 1990: 59).

An episode narrated by one of our interviewees reinforces Halbwachs' concept of autobiographical memory:

My great-grandmother came to Brazil around 1910 and was never able to get used to the weather here. She never stopped complaining about the heat, the food, the insects. She complained about everything. She was constantly fanning herself and saying that Brazil was hell. I remember her every time I see a fan. She fanned herself till she was 90! (...) But it must have been hard to live in a foreign country... I can just imagine: Brazil must have been a scary place for Europeans.

Collective memory as a continuous social construction

Collective memory is a "living history". In Halbwachs words (1990, p. 89):

Collective memory is a continuous current of thought, of a continuity that is by no means artificial, because it conserves nothing from the past except the parts which still live, or are capable of living in the conscience of the group.

Halbwachs argues that collective memory reconstructs the past by adapting images of old facts to the needs of the present. That is, society remembers the past according to present concerns. Halbwachs believes that the past is not static. Rather, it changes according to the requirements of the present.

In other words: Past is a collective construction designed in and for the present. Once recreated, however, its effects are very real/concrete: it moulds the group's vision of the world and guides its actions.

So far, we can conclude that past shapes and, at the same time, is shaped by our understanding of the world. Past is the result of what we do and what we consider to be important.

Collective memory and space

Material world and sense of order

Halbwachs' ideas on collective memory and space raise interesting questions about the material world (1990:chapter 4).

The author presents us with the curious idea formulated by Auguste Comte, according to whom our mental stability arises in large part from the fact that our everyday objects change little and give us a permanent and stable image. Halbwachs compares these objects to a silent and motionless society, indifferent to our agitation and change of mood and, as such, responsible for the transmission of the senses of order and quietude (1990: 131).

He recognizes the existence of a strong relationship between people and those things that are familiar to them. This is shown in his comments on how we feel when we find ourselves in an unfamiliar material environment:

(...) before adapting to it, we go through a period of uncertainty, as if we had left behind our entire personality (Halbwachs, 1990: 131).

The situation presented by Halbwachs brings us to the memories of one of our interviewees, just as she arrived to live in the United States:

I took things to make my home feel like a Brazilian home, such as Brazilian engravings. But everything around me looked so different. I started getting a little depressed (...) The oven was electric and I didn't know how to use it. There was a smoke detector so I could no longer take hot showers with the door open or fry a steak. There were no drains in the floor (...) So, when I went into the supermarket and I saw a shopping cart it was an enormous relief! It was familiar to me! I definitely knew how that worked! I walked around with the shopping cart as if it were an old friend, I swear!

According to Halbwachs, "usual images of the external world are inseparable from us" (1990: 131). In other words, the physical environment and the artifacts that participate in

our everyday lives end up becoming part of our identity. Further more, this explains our interviewees' feelings towards some of their memory artifacts:

There was a tree in my yard: an almond tree with a swing my father built which I loved. But the tree began to rot and my father decided to cut it down (...) I almost died when I saw it all sawed up. It was awful! I was devastated for years and years... I even missed the sound of my mother sweeping the floor and gathering the leaves.

I think those things are part of me. (...) I still have my first electric razor. I mean, how many times was it in my hands as I was shaving and thinking of a job interview or a party where everything is supposed to turn out perfect?

I keep a little cushion from the time I was a little girl (...) I only sleep if I have my cushion. As time went by, my cushion accompanied me because I never let go of it. In the end I grew up and today I have my daughters and my dear cushion!

Halbwachs asks and answers himself:

Why do we become attached to objects? Why do we wish that they remain unchanged, and continue to be in our company? We disregard comfort and aesthetics. Our material surroundings carry our own marks and those of others at the same time. Our home, our furniture (...) reminds us of our family and our friends that we were used to seeing within that frame (1990: 131).

The passage above is well illustrated by our interviewees:

There is this really old fan at home, and every time I look at it I remember my great-grandmother, because it was her fan (...) it is an old fan that has no more practical use. It is not pretty either. We don't use it anymore. It is there as a memento, you know?

About two years ago I found a piece of tile just like the ones that were in the bathroom of the house I grew up in. It is my most precious belonging.

Halbwachs strengthens the idea that material things bring a sense of balance and stability when he examines a situation in which a small group suffers a shock:

Life around us continues as if nothing happened (...) while we, our family, our friends feel as if a catastrophic wind were blowing. (1990:135)

The author concludes that peoples' indifference, as well as everything that is inert, can hurt us but can also calm us down and give us balance.

Things as they are

Halbwachs asserts that:

(...) every collective unfolds within a spatial framework. Now space is a reality that endures: our impressions rush by ... we can understand how we recapture the past only by understanding how it is, in effect, preserved by our physical surroundings. It is to space - the space we occupy, traverse, have continual access to, or can at any time reconstruct in thought and imagination - that we must turn our attention ... (Halbwachs, 1990:143)

In a rather curious passage, Halbwachs suggests that in order to see only the physical and formal qualities of things, we would have to adopt the attitude of physicists and artists. He claims that only under the "influence of painter' society" we would see things "not as they are, but rather as they are perceived by those who dedicate themselves exclusively to reproducing images" (1990:144).

At the end of the book, the reader is invited to do the following memory exercise:

Now concentrate, close your eyes, go back in time as far as possible, as much as your thought can fixate on scenes or people that are preserved in your memory (1990:160).

How can we not agree with Halbwachs that we will always find ourselves in places we know, in places we can locate and in places, which are part of our material environment?

Conclusion

Maurice Halbwachs articulated memory as conscious, collective, and purposeful. Rather than being a passive, individual phenomenon, memory instead is located within a web of social practices.

He demonstrates that we live and remember in society. He also makes us realize that we live and remember based on things designers help to create.

According to the preliminary findings of our study, memory artifacts represent significant people, places and moments that are pleasant to remember. They bring a sense of integrity, comfort, enjoyment, belonging and purpose to our lives.

We can therefore say that the goal of Design could be to create products that turn themselves into memorable things. Memorable things, not only for their good form but above all, for the significant experiences they can foster.

In order to reach this goal, designers must observe that an artifact becomes memorable through the use one makes of it, as well as the value one gives to it, both of which escape the designer's control. Yet, if we take into consideration that design is a thinking process involving planning with intention and purpose, why not believe designers can plan with the intention and purpose of building and reinforcing relationships and of fostering meaningful social experiences?

In the remaining space, we would like to highlight the above idea by answering a question of one of our interviewees:

This pillow, this pacifier, this rattle remind me of my son when he was a baby. These mementos are witnesses to the strongest love relationship I have ever experienced. Who would ever imagine that they would be so meaningful to me?

We would very much like to answer some day: a designer.

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